

NDAC/LO/087
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ERRATUM:

Specification of output for the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator as required for the Double Star analysis (NDAC/LO/076)

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Equations (2a)-(2b) in the paper above are unfortunately wrong. The exponent at the end of the equations should be -1 , not $-\frac{1}{2}$. The correct expressions are:

$$\bar{\beta}_4 = R (\tilde{\beta}_4 \hat{\beta}_4 + \tilde{\beta}_5 \hat{\beta}_5) (\tilde{\beta}_4^2 + \tilde{\beta}_5^2)^{-1} \quad (2a)$$

$$\bar{\beta}_5 = R (\tilde{\beta}_4 \hat{\beta}_5 - \tilde{\beta}_5 \hat{\beta}_4) (\tilde{\beta}_4^2 + \tilde{\beta}_5^2)^{-1} \quad (2b)$$